

The soil pit method: Measuring crop root depth and distribution

Problem

Root systems and their interactions with the soil are crucial for crop performance, through the capture of water and nutrients. These root functions are important for improving resource use efficiency and enhancing crop resilience against climate change. There can be many limitations to crop rooting, such as nutrition, over or under supply of water, soil compaction and structure or agronomic management.

Solution

To evaluate how effectively a crop has established its root system in a specific environment, and to assess potential differences between varieties or the impact of treatments such as cultivation methods or agrochemicals, it is necessary to observe root development directly in the field. The soil pit method, also known as soil profile wall method, was developed to assess root distribution in different crop species. The method presented here is based on the ARVALIS standard operating procedure shared during the Root2Res project.

Principle

The soil pit method is a field-based approach designed to reveal the spatial distribution of crop roots within the soil profile. By exposing and visually assessing root systems in situ, the method provides insight into how roots grow and respond to physical conditions and management practices. It offers a direct and practical means of evaluating rooting patterns and depths in real agronomic conditions.

Benefits and weaknesses

The soil pit method enables the measurement of root distribution at varying depths, offering valuable insights into how soil structure and composition influence root development. However, the method is both time-consuming and destructive, making it less suitable for large-scale screening or breeding programmes. It is best applied in detailed agronomic or systems-based studies where a deeper understanding of root - soil interactions is desired but fewer samples are needed.

Applicability box

Theme: Root measurements

Relevance: The soil pit method enables in-situ observation of root depth and distribution down to 1-2 metres.

Best in: All arable crops; between flowering and immediately after harvest

Measured traits:

- Presence or absence of roots per cm²
- Percentage of roots per cm of soil depth

Required time:

- Digging the pit: 1h
- Preparation and measurement: 3h

Figure 1: Soil pit with attached grid.

Practical recommendations

- Select a location that is representative of the entire plot before digging the soil pit.
- Align the pit and grid consistently with the crop rows to ensure uniform sampling.
- The pit should typically measure around 1 metre in width and 1 to 2 metres in depth (Figure 1).
- Carefully scrape the vertical face of the pit using a knife to expose the root structure (Figure 2).
- Attach a grid to the exposed surface and record the presence or absence of roots in each square (Figure 3). Grid squares can range in size from 2 cm to 10 cm.
- For each depth interval, calculate and express the percentage of squares containing roots.

Figure 2: Carefully scrape the pit wall with a knife.

Figure 3: Assess the presence or absence of roots in each square.

Further information

- Böhm, W. (1979). Profile Wall Methods. In: Methods of Studying Root Systems. Ecological Studies, vol 33. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-67282-8_6

About this practice abstract and Root2Resilience

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Project website: root2res.eu

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